

**TREATMENT TACTICS FOR ACUTE PARAPROCTITIS
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To determine the optimal tactics for the diagnosis and treatment of acute paraproctitis in pregnant women, taking into account the gestational age, the nature of the inflammatory process, and minimising the risk to the foetus.

ABSTRACT

Acute paraproctitis is one of the most common purulent-inflammatory diseases of the rectum and perirectal tissue, accounting for up to 30–40% of all cases of proctological surgical pathology. The development of this disease in pregnant women presents a particular clinical and therapeutic challenge, as the inflammatory process and the need for surgical intervention are associated with risks for both the mother and the foetus. Physiological changes in the body of a pregnant woman - hormonal shifts, decreased immune reactivity, slowed intestinal motility, and venous stasis in the small pelvis - create favourable conditions for the development of paraproctitis and aggravation of its course. Despite the existence of uniform principles for the surgical treatment of acute paraproctitis, pregnant women require an individual, gentle approach that takes into account the gestational age, the degree of inflammation, the location of the abscess, and the general condition of the patient.

Introduction

Acute paraproctitis is one of the most common purulent-inflammatory diseases of the rectum and perirectal tissue, accounting for up to 30–40% of all cases of proctological surgical pathology. The development of this disease in pregnant women presents a particular clinical and therapeutic challenge, as the inflammatory process and the need for surgical intervention are associated with risks for both the mother and the foetus. Physiological changes in the body of a pregnant woman - hormonal shifts, decreased immune reactivity, slowed intestinal motility, and venous stasis in the small pelvis - create favourable conditions for the development of paraproctitis and aggravation of its course. Despite the existence of uniform principles for the surgical treatment of acute paraproctitis, pregnant women require an individual, gentle approach that takes into account the gestational age, the degree of inflammation, the location of the abscess, and the general condition of the patient.

Objective

To determine the optimal tactics for the diagnosis and treatment of acute paraproctitis in pregnant women, taking into account the gestational age, the nature of the inflammatory process, and minimising the risk to the foetus.

Materials and methods

A retrospective analysis was conducted of 42 clinical cases of acute paraproctitis in pregnant women who were treated in the coloproctology department and obstetric hospital between 2015 and 2024. The patients' ages ranged from 19 to 38 years. Clinical manifestations, laboratory and instrumental data, anaesthesiological features, surgical methods and postoperative course were studied.

All patients were divided into three groups depending on the gestational age:

Group I — up to 12 weeks (n=10),

Group II — 13–28 weeks (n=17),

Group III — more than 28 weeks (n=15).

All women underwent ultrasound examination of the pelvic organs and perianal region, bacteriological examination of secretions, and complete blood count. The choice of treatment method was determined by the location of the purulent focus (subcutaneous, ischiorectal, pelviorectal, submucosal paraproctitis), the severity of intoxication, and the condition of the foetus.

Results

In 64% of pregnant women, the disease was acute with a typical clinical picture -pain in the anorectal region, hyperthermia, oedema, and tissue hyperemia. In 21%, the course was mild, which led to late diagnosis (2–3 weeks after the onset of the disease). Surgical treatment was performed in 35 (83%) women. In 7 patients with superficial abscesses and no signs of systemic infection, a conservative wait-and-see approach was used with antibacterial and anti-inflammatory therapy, physiotherapy, and careful monitoring. Conduction or infiltration anaesthesia with lidocaine solution was predominantly used, taking into account the safety of the foetus; general anaesthesia was used only in extreme cases (3 patients). After opening and draining the abscesses, most patients (90%) had a favourable postoperative course. Premature labour was observed in 2 women (5%), which was probably due to severe intoxication and fever before the operation. No fatalities were recorded. In the first and second trimesters, complete incision and sanitation of the focus with removal of the crypt was preferred; in the third trimester, limited drainage followed by radical treatment after delivery was preferred.

Discussion

The treatment of acute paraproctitis in pregnant women should be based on the principles of emergency surgery, but with maximum preservation of the mother's and foetus's health. Delaying surgery increases the risk of generalisation of infection, sepsis, and premature delivery. However, not every intervention needs to be radical: in late pregnancy, limited incision and drainage of the purulent focus is preferable, with delayed excision of the internal opening of the fistula after delivery. A multidisciplinary approach is essential, with the patient being jointly managed by a proctologist, obstetrician-gynaecologist and anaesthesiologist. Antibiotic therapy is selected with the safety of the foetus in mind (penicillins, second- and third-generation cephalosporins). The use of metronidazole and aminoglycosides in the first trimester is contraindicated. Particular attention is paid to the prevention of thrombosis, maintaining normal haemodynamics and adequate pain relief, as stress and pain syndrome can provoke uterine contractions.

Conclusions

1. Acute paraproctitis in pregnant women requires early diagnosis and a differentiated approach to the choice of treatment tactics.
2. Surgical treatment remains the method of choice, especially in the presence of fluctuation and symptoms of intoxication.
3. Radical intervention is possible in early pregnancy; in late pregnancy, limited drainage followed by radical treatment after delivery is preferable.
4. Optimal results are achieved with a multidisciplinary approach and close cooperation between obstetricians and coloproctologists.
5. Timely sanitation of the infection site and rational antibiotic therapy ensure a favourable outcome for both the mother and the foetus.

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